

Adapting self-attention algorithms to chemogenomic spaces to predict antimicrobial resistance and accelerate antibiotic discovery

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Abstract. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a critical global health threat, directly responsible for an estimated 1.27 million deaths and indirectly linked to another 4.95 million in 2019, according to the World Health Organization. By 2050, AMR could claim 10 million lives annually and cause \$3.4 trillion in yearly GDP losses. Traditional antimicrobial drug discovery remains time-consuming and costly, relying on extensive in vitro testing. Recently, machine learning has emerged as a powerful alternative, with two distinct approaches: one relies on bacterial DNA to calculate resistance scores; the other focuses on the chemical structures of compounds. Both require new assay testing for novel antibiotics or pathogens. This work proposes a method that combines bacterial DNA sequences with antimicrobial chemical structures to predict activity without additional in vitro tests. Using a self-attention-based transformer algorithm, the model identifies key patterns in both DNA and chemicals. Trained on *E. coli* data, it can predict the activity of new antibiotics against unfamiliar pathogens, pinpoint AMR-related gene locations, and assist drug discovery.

Keywords: antimicrobial resistance · transformers · drug discovery

1 Introduction

This project addresses the problem of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) [1]. A traditional approach to AMR prediction involves antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST), which is accurate but time-consuming and costly. Recently, several computational methods have been proposed to reduce the need for laboratory testing. These methods can be grouped into two categories. The first group (“Type I”) [2, 5] uses a fixed antibiotic compound and treats the pathogen genome as a variable. After ASTs are performed on pathogens with a given compound, machine learning is applied to predict AMR for similar pathogens. The second group (“Type II”) [3, 4] uses a fixed pathogen and tests it against multiple chemical compounds. After ASTs, a machine learning model is trained to predict AMR for structurally similar chemicals against the same pathogen. Both approaches support knowledge transfer from experimental data to unseen data, but each has limitations: Type I generalizes to new pathogens but not new compounds, while Type II generalizes to new compounds but not new pathogens.

In this work, we propose a combined approach—“Type III”—which enables prediction for both new chemicals and new pathogens, covering a cross-domain input space (Fig. 1). Simply combining encoders used in Type I and II methods is insufficient: such a model cannot effectively capture interactions between DNA segments and chemical substructures. Modern language models based on self-attention (transformers) [8] excel at identifying dependencies in textual data. While DNA and chemical structures are not natural languages, applying transformer-based models to their combined representations is a promising direction. In the following sections, we describe how transformers can be adapted to build a Type III AMR prediction system and present results from a working prototype.

Fig. 1: AMR prediction methods comparison

2 System design

To apply a transformer to both DNA and chemical structures, each must be represented as a sequence of “words.” For chemicals, the SMILES representation is a natural choice, with each symbol’s encoding learned during training. DNA is more challenging. A full genomic sequence consists of millions of nucleotides from only four base types, which provide limited information individually. Genes would be better “words,” but are not always annotated. As a compromise, we split the genomic sequence into chunks, hoping some capture meaningful traits. However, fixed-size chunks are fragile: a single deletion or insertion can shift all boundaries, resulting in dissimilar representations for similar sequences.

To address this, we use a technique from document search—splitting character sequences into pseudo-random chunks using Rabin fingerprints [6]. This method tolerates insertions and deletions by creating more stable chunk boundaries. For example, if we split a 100-character string into fixed-size chunks of

10 characters, we get 10 segments. Inserting a character at the beginning shifts all chunks, replacing all 10. In contrast, Rabin-based chunking would still produce about 10 chunks on average, but most would remain unchanged, preserving similarity. Applied to DNA, this produces a more language-like structure, where recurring segments can retain meaning across sequences (Fig. 2). Once tokenized, the input can be processed with self-attention (Fig. 3) to identify patterns and relationships that traditional algorithms may miss.

Fig. 2: Splitting data with Rabin fingerprints

3 Testing

We built a simple proof-of-concept neural network to evaluate our approach (Fig. 4). We used public data from [5], comprising 1934 *E. coli* strains tested against 12 antibiotics: cefotaxime (CTX), ceftazidime (CTZ), ampicillin (AMP), amoxicillin (AMX), amoxicillin-clavulanate (AMC), piperacillin-tazobactam (TZP), cefuroxime (CXM), cephalothin (CET), gentamicin (GEN), tobramycin (TBM), trimethoprim (TMP), and ciprofloxacin (CIP). DNA sequences were downloaded from the European Nucleotide Archive, encoded as 4 nucleotides per byte, and split into pseudo-random chunks of approximately 128 bytes.

For each antibiotic, the following procedure was used:

1. Exclude all ASTs involving the selected compound.
2. From the set of pathogens tested with that compound, exclude 5%.
3. Train the model on the remaining data for 50 epochs.
4. Test the model on the excluded pathogen-compound pairs.
5. Repeat steps 2–4 using 20-fold cross-validation.

For comparison, we also evaluated Random Forest and Support Vector Machine models (Fig. 5). Despite limited training data, our transformer-based model demonstrated successful knowledge transfer and outperformed the baselines.

Fig. 3: Basic concept

Fig. 4: Implementation details

Fig. 5: AMR prediction accuracy for 12 chemicals

Fig. 6: Integration with SyntheMol

4 Applications

We envision three applications of our approach: drug repurposing, novel drug discovery, and AMR gene exploration. To evaluate these, we retrained the model on the full dataset.

For drug repurposing, we used a balanced set of AST results for the BW25113 strain of *E. coli* [4], which was not part of the training data. We selected compounds with Tversky similarity >0.5 to the training set (due to its limited size),

resulting in 26 test cases where both the pathogen and compounds were unseen. The model correctly predicted 21 responses (80%), a promising result for a proof-of-concept.

For drug discovery, we combined our model with SyntheMol [7], a generative AI tool (Fig. 6). It generated several thousand drug candidates predicted to be active against BW25113. Without synthesis capabilities, we approximated validation by comparing to known antibiotics. From 6000 compounds tested against BW25113 [4], we identified 18 with Tversky similarity >0.8 to any generated candidate. All 18 were effective, supporting the model’s predictive validity.

An additional benefit of self-attention models is the availability of attention maps, which highlight important input regions. In genomic data, these may correspond to AMR-related genes. We extracted the top 100 positions with the highest attention scores and found that at least 11 overlapped with known AMR-associated gene locations. While this requires further investigation, it indicates that the attention maps can assist in the discovery of other AMR-related genes.

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